

Fundamental study on CFRP strengthening method for bolted connections with U-shaped carbon tow

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Abstract

Although bearing connections are used in spatial structures and transmission towers, improving load-carrying capacity and/or strengthening it against earthquakes and external service loads are often difficult. While bolt strength can be enhanced using high-tension bolts, there is currently no effective method to address issues such as end failure and bearing stress fracture in bearing bolt connections. In addition, strengthening by adding steel plates increases the weight of the building, among other problems. To solve this problem, we propose a carbon tow application that prevents rupture before the bolts fail in shear. Large tow and epoxy resin were used to manufacture the specimens. The experiments showed that the shear strength of the specimens with strengthening was higher than those without strengthening. Moreover, the bolt holes expanded by approximately 35% in the experiment without strengthening, but the deformation significantly decreased with the strengthening of the carbon tow, confirming the strengthening effect.

Keywords: angle steel, bearing bolt connection, strengthening, CFRP, carbon tow

1. Introduction

Bearing bolted connections are commonly used in spatial structures and transmission towers. However, in recent years, natural disasters and changes in external forces have required improved seismic retrofit. Several studies have been conducted to strengthen steel connections. Kishiki et al. [1, 2] proposed a strengthening method of bolted connections by adding parallel members and corner welding. The studies confirmed that additional members increase the ultimate strength of the existing bolted connection. Similarly, Nakamura et al. [3] show the adhesively bonded steel plates for transmission towers to improve the deformation performance of the shaft section. In the research on the repair of corroded steel members, the uses of CFRP reinforcement for bolted angle connections were examined. Matsumoto et al. [4] proposed a CFRP repair method employing the VaRTM method and demonstrated its effectiveness.

Currently, bolt strength in support joints can be enhanced by employing high-strength bolts. However, this approach is ineffective in addressing the end or support failure. Additionally, reinforcement using steel plates increases weight, leading to other complications. To overcome these, this study proposes a CFRP reinforcement method utilizing continuous fiber, which prevents bolt rupture before shear failure. This method is universally applicable, eliminating the need for welding or adding significant weight to the structure. The effectiveness of the proposed reinforcement method is verified through one-surface shear tests presented in this paper.

2. Proposed strengthening method

2.1 Strengthening overview

Figure 1 illustrates an overview of the proposed strengthening method. In this method, bolts are covered with steel caps to adapt the various bolthead angles and reinforced by hooking U-shaped continuous fibers impregnated with resin using the VaRTM method. The fibers were wrapped around the bolt caps and cured.

Figure 1: Proposed strengthening method

2.2 Specimen

This section discusses the bearing strength and anchorage length of continuous fibers.

2.2.1 The bearing strength of continuous fibers

The specimen is designed so that the continuous fibers do not rupture before the bolts fail in shear, referring to the Design Standards on Structures for Transmission [5].

Table 1: Variables

σ_{ba}	: Allowable bearing stress of the steel
A_{ba}	: Bearing area of the steel
A_e	: Effective cross-sectional area of the steel
F_u	: Tensile strength of the steel
m	: Number of the shear planes
A_{bs}	: Net Tensile stress area of the bolt / Cross-sectional area of the bolt
F_{bu}	: Ultimate tensile strength of the bolt
P_{ct}	: Tensile strength per single carbon tow
n_{ct}	: Number of the carbon tows

- Bearing strength of steel members

$$P_1 = 1.25\sigma_{ba} \cdot A_{ba} \quad (1)$$

- Maximum bearing capacity of steel member regarding its effective cross-sectional area

$$P_2 = A_e \cdot F_u \quad (2)$$

- Maximum shear strength of high-tension bolts

$$P_3 = 0.6m \cdot A_{bs} \cdot F_{bu} \quad (3)$$

- Strength of continuous fibers

$$P_4 = P_{ct} \cdot n_{ct} \quad (4)$$

The number of continuous fiber tows and the bearing strength were determined so that equation (5) was satisfied in the above four equations.

$$P_1 < P_2 < P_3 < P_4 \quad (5)$$

2.2.2 anchorage length of continuous fibers

Two cases were considered to determine the required anchorage length of carbon tow for strengthening during molding: one based on the adhesive area and the other on the effective adhesion area, measured as 260 mm and 350 mm, respectively.

3. Manufacturing method

Figure 2 shows a typical manufacturing process.

Figure 2: Manufacturing process of the specimen (a) VaRTM method (b) winding of the tow (c) blasted surface of the steel (d) adhesive application (e) manufactured test specimen

Since it is difficult to impregnate the carbon tow with resin and adhere it to the specimen under tension, a preform process was carried out. Holes were created to accommodate bonding lengths of 260 mm and 350 mm, and nails were positioned to guide the carbon tow. The carbon tow length corresponding to each fusing length was calculated.

Figure 2(a) shows the photograph of VaRTM method. The tow was wound around a pipe serving as a mandrel, and resin impregnation was carried out using the VaRTM method. The standard VaRTM method keeps the material in a vacuum until the resin hardens. However, in this study, the vacuum was released after resin impregnation, and the material was removed to form the tow.

Figure 2(b) shows the lamination of the resin-impregnated tow. The carbon tow was molded without twisting. After molding, the tow was cured for approximately one week to allow the resin to harden.

Figure 2(c) shows the steel's blasted surface. The bonding surfaces were treated using an electrical power tool to make a blasted surface. Bolts were fastened utilizing a torque wrench on all specimens, with an introduced tension of 18 kN for the reinforcement.

Figure 2(d) shows an adhesive application. Epoxy resin (E258R) was applied to the steel and the carbon tow. Following the application, the specimens were cured for approximately one week to allow the adhesive to harden fully. The test specimen after fabrication is shown in Figure 2(e).

4. Experimental test

4.1 Specimen configuration

Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram of the specimens. Tables 2 ~ 4 show the properties of the materials used. The specimens consist of steel plates, 25x100mm as the gusset plates and 9x50mm as the brace member, connected with M16 high-strength steel bolts. A cover plate reinforces the right side of the specimens to prevent yielding. The 260 and 350mm anchorage lengths were adopted to judge the bonding strength performance.

Figure 3: Specimen configuration [unit: mm] (a) NS-1~3 (b) 260-1~3 (c) 350-1~3 (d) side elevation (350-1~3)

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the steel

Grade	Yield point	Tensile strength	elongation
SS400 (steel plates)	353 MPa	465 MPa	28%
F10T (bolts)	1036 MPa	1090 MPa	20%

Table 3: Mechanical properties of the carbon tow

Product	Tensile strength	Tensile modulus	Density	Fineness
PX 35	4137 MPa	242 GPa	1.81 g/cm ³	3750 tex

Table 4. Mechanical properties of the epoxy resin

Product	Tensile strength	Tensile modulus	Poisson's ratio
E205	49.5 MPa	2.51 GPa	0.40
E258R	30.9 MPa	3.80 GPa	0.36

4.2 Testing procedures

Figure 4 shows the experimental setup. Tests were conducted using a hydraulic universal testing machine, with three specimens tested for each parameter. The tensile loads were applied monotonically. The applied load, several positions' strain, and relative displacement were measured during the test using a built-in loadcell, strain gauges, and wire-type displacement transducer, respectively. For the NS specimens, loading was stopped when +10 mm displacement occurred after bolt slippage was confirmed for safety reasons. For the strengthened specimens, loading was stopped before the maximum shear strength ($P_3 = 120.64$ kN) of the high-tension bolt in the strengthened section was reached.

Figure 4: Test set-up (a) Specimen without strengthening (b) Specimen with strengthening

4.3 Test results

Figure 5 shows the load-displacement relationship. The figure shows the strength (P_1 - P_3) corresponding to the failure mode of the steel. In specimens 260-1 and 350-2, unstable relative displacement responses (noise) were observed because of the problem with the wire displacement transducer. Focusing on the NS specimens, the stiffness of all specimens gradually decreased when the load was around 5-10 kN, then increased again at around 20 kN and showed a gentle curve thereafter. In the range of 10 kN to 20 kN, it is estimated that slip deformation occurred as the bolts transitioned to a bearing state. In addition, once the stiffness exceeded P_1 , the bearing strength of the steel, it decreased and then showed a curved behavior up to P_2 . Focusing on the reinforced specimens, although there was some scatter in the measured values, stiffness due to slip deformation occurred at around 10 kN. It showed roughly linear behavior until it exceeded 100 kN. Also, the 260 and 350 specimens exhibit similar behavior, indicating no significant difference in the strengthening effect.

Figure 5: Load-displacement relationship

Figure 6 shows the load-strain relationship at the strain measurement points. In the NS specimens, the compressive strain increases after reaching P_1 . On the other hand, the strengthened specimens show an increase in compressive strain at higher loads. This indicates that strengthening increases the strength of the bearing area and suppresses the progression of local strain next to the bolt holes.

Figure 6: Load-strain relationship

5. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates a new strengthening method for the bearing connection using the tailor-made carbon fiber attachment the authors proposed. The tensile tests of a bolted connection with/without strengthening and significant strengthening effect were observed; deformation was especially prevented, and the load capacity increased. However, there are no representative differences between the anchorage length parameters, 260 and 350mm so the authors will investigate reasonable anchorage details and design methods in the future.

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